

Supplementary Figures to: Metabolic modeling reveals the aging-associated decline of host-microbiome metabolic interactions in mice

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Suppl. Fig. 1: **A** Study setup and **B** Metagenomics workflow and Metagenome characterization. Abundance of metagenomics reads derived from microbes **C** or mouse DNA **D**. Read depths and host reads did not differ significantly between age groups according to pairwise comparisons using the Kruskal–Wallis test. **E** Alpha diversity derived from metagenomic reads mapped against MAGs. Metagenomic-derived alpha diversity did not differ significantly between the age groups according to pairwise comparisons using the Kruskal–Wallis test. **F** Abundance profile of the 60 most abundant MAGs in the full cohort. Bacteroidota predominated in the cohort while some species in Bacillota and other phyla contributed only a small amount to the total microbiome biomass. Phylum colors are reused from main Fig. 1A.

Host-microbiome interaction:

A

B

Suppl. Fig. 2: **A** High-level pathway overview of host–microbiome abundance. Sum of $-\log_{10}(\text{FDR-adjusted } p\text{-values})$ for the odds ratios of correlation-based host–microbiome pathway interactions. **B** HUMAnN3 predicted microbial functions (MetaCyc) correlated to host colon transcription (GO biological processes) show comparable associations to MAG-based analysis in Fig. 2B. We employed the Biobakery3 pipeline to infer functional and taxonomic associations directly from quality controlled metagenomic reads and compared those results to our MAG based approach. We observed similar, yet fewer associations when correlating host to microbiome functions. Bacterial pyruvate fermentation and co-factor biosynthesis were negatively correlated with host side neuron survival. Microbial fatty acids were found positively associated with colon immune processes (MHC class I) and negatively with transcription regulation. These HUMAnN3 based analysis results were generally in concordance, although much less detailed, to our MAG and metabolic model derived host microbiome correlations (see Fig. 2B).

Suppl. Fig. 3: A Randomization of germfree mouse analysis (Fig. 3D). The identification of significant differences in microbiome dependence between significantly up-regulated, down-regulated and unregulated genes was repeated after randomization of gene assignments. To this end, gene labels were randomly swapped in the list of differentially expressed genes and the number of cases with significant differences in microbiome dependency of the associated reactions repeated again. This was repeated a thousand times. During randomization we found on average 8.6 cases of significant differences and at most 18, compared to the 21 cases we observed with the original data (red dashed line). In the original analysis we observed nine cases in which up- or down-regulated genes showed a higher microbiome dependency in their association reactions compared to un-regulated genes, three genes in which unregulated genes showed a higher microbiome dependency and nine cases in which there was a significant difference in microbiome dependency between the reactions associated with up- and down-regulated genes. **B** Association between model-predicted microbiome dependency of metabolites in blood and explained variation of serum concentrations of the corresponding metabolite by microbiome composition in a human cohort. Each dot corresponds to a metabolite. The association between microbiome dependency and explained variance is significant using Spearman's correlation ($\rho=0.43$, $p\text{-value}=1.5\times 10^{-3}$). To predict microbiome dependence of metabolites, we iteratively added an exchange reaction for each metabolite exchanged via blood in the metamodel and used flux balance analysis to maximize its outflow. Subsequently, we blocked all microbiome reactions and maximized the outflow again. If the outflow without the microbiome was below 50% of the outflow compared to the wild type simulation, a metabolite was assumed microbiome dependent. Determining microbiome dependence across all 52 mice we obtained a microbiome dependency frequency for each metabolite. Subsequently, metabolites were filtered for those that occurred in at least 40 mice. Variance in human serum metabolite concentration explained by microbiome composition was obtained from Bar et al. (DOI: 10.1038/s41586-020-2896-2) and mapped via HMDB IDs to the corresponding microbiome dependence of metabolites in blood predicted by the metamodel. We only considered metabolites from Bar et al. for which the statistical model to assess explained variance yielded a significant fit at $p\leq 0.1$. The corresponding data can be found in Supplementary Table S3.10.

Functional changes in the microbiome depend on host age

Suppl. Fig. 4: **A** MetaPhlAn4 derived species with significant changes in abundance with host age. The MetaPhlAn-based approach identified 335 bacteria at the species level of which 69 were found differentially abundant with age. The species *Lactobacillus johnsonii* matched the MAG based analysis (Fig. 4A). However, due to different taxonomic databases and methods of annotation the resulting species names might vary. On phylum level the overall aging pattern of both MetaPhlAn and MAG-based taxonomic analysis yielded comparable results, which was a general decrease of *Bacillota* spec. and an increase of *Bacteroidota* spec. with host age. **B** Age-associated changes in metabolic fluxes within the community. **C** Relative abundance of universal adaptive strategies in microbiome communities by age. We investigated the extent to which aging-associated shifts in microbiome ecology were related to species-level ecological strategies according to the universal adaptive strategies theory (UAST) framework, which categorizes species into ruderals, competitors, and stress tolerators^{44,45}. Within this framework, ruderals are species that are first colonizers of niches characterized by rapid growth and low catabolic diversity, competitors are species that can outcompete other species through direct antimicrobial effectors and broader resource utilization, and stress tolerators are species that are resistant to stress. We observed a significant increase in the ruderal strategy with age, whereas stress tolerators and competitors significantly decreased in frequency. While having high growth potential, the reduced catabolic diversity of ruderals and their focus on *de novo* colonization of niches makes them poor interaction partners in metabolic cross-feeding interaction, thereby reducing the overall capacity of the community to grow due to less efficient utilization of dietary resources. **D** Comparison of community growth rates derived from FBA or PTR. Growth rate estimates from metabolic modeling community simulations and metagenomic peak-to-trough analysis were strongly and positively correlated and indicated reduced growth rates of models or MAGs in older mice. **4E & F** Change of microbiome community growth rate upon removal of a single MAG from the community. The y-axis shows the difference of community growth rate compared to the full community while the x-axis names the MAG that was removed (**E**) or the age group of the host (**F**). MAGs that were found to be significantly increased in abundance in old mice are colored red and those that were found significantly decreased in old mice are colored in blue. Overall, community growth was impacted negatively when MAGs that go down with age were removed, while the community growth increased upon deletion of aging up-regulated MAGs. Thus, MAGs with reduced abundance during aging tend to have a positive impact on community productivity and MAGs that increase in abundance with age tend to have a negative impact. Looking at the effect of species removal, we observed removal from young (2 months) communities in general leads to a drop of community productivity (i.e. all species rely on each other) whereas removal of species from old communities (24 & 30 months) increased community growth rates (i.e. species mostly compete with each other). FDR corrected p-values in **F**: 2 months $p > 0.98$, 9 months $p < 4.6e-05$, 15 months $p < 6.0e-16$, 24 months $p = 5.5e-16$, 30 months $p = 5.5e-16$. **G** Changes in D-galactose concentration with age. The metabolomics derived D-galactose concentration in mouse feces increased with age (Spearman's $\rho = 0.22$, $p = 0.04$ [not FDR-adjusted]).

Host aging

Suppl. Fig. 5: Aging-associated transcriptomic changes across host tissues. Each row represents a gene that shows common expression changes across all tissues studied (see Supplementary Table S5.7 for the complete list and Tables S5.8 and S5.9 for GO enrichment).

Host–microbiome associations and aging:

Suppl. Fig. 6: Host-Microbiome associations in aging. **A–E** Strong host–microbiome correlations stratified by age group. **A** Frequency of microbiome–colon correlations stratified by age group. Significance was tested with Pearson’s Chi-squared test with Yates’ continuity correction and Bonferroni multiple testing correction. **B** Liver transcripts correlated with microbiome reactions. **C** Liver transcripts partially correlated with microbiome reactions, corrected for sequencing batch. **D** Brain transcripts correlated with microbiome reactions. **E** Brain transcripts partially correlated with microbiome reactions, corrected for sequencing batch. **F–G** Organ-specific gene expression changes with age in GO biological processes that were also correlated with microbiome metabolic functions (**F** = liver, **G** = brain).